

Parenting Education: An Effective Strategy For Breaking Intergenerational Pattern And Fostering Children's Mental Health

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ABSTRACT

The transmission of trauma, beliefs and behavioural patterns across generations which is known as Intergenerational pattern plays a crucial role in shaping the psychological well-being of children in Nigeria. This paper examines how family dynamics, children psycho-social issues, cultural intricacies and their implications on mental health, and how these patterns often perpetuate cycles of psychological distress among the young ones and the 'generations unborn'. The manifestation of Intergenerational trauma and its consequences in Nigerian children's emotional, behavioural, cognitive and social functioning cannot be overemphasized. Based on recent studies and culturally relevant frameworks, the analysis identifies key psycho-social issues such as Post-traumatic Stress Disorder(PTSD), anxiety, aggression, depression, suicidal behaviour, poor academic engagement and substance abuse, among others. The paper also expatiates on implications for mental health counseling in Nigeria, emphasizing the urgent need for trauma-informed, attachment based and culturally sensitive interventions. The study advocates the need for integration of family-focused therapy in child mental health services, comprehensive parental psycho-education, community collaboration and effort of religious leaders to foster the mental well-being of these young ones.

Keywords: Intergenerational Pattern, Children's Psycho-social Issues, Parental Education, Mental Health Counselling, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, increasing attention has been paid to the influence of parental dynamics and education on the psycho-social development of children. Issues are arising on parenting styles (authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, and neglectful) which are often passed down from generation to generation and have direct or indirect influence positively or negatively on the children's upbringing. These behaviours often manifest unconsciously to the extent that parents may repeat the behaviours and attitudes they experienced, even if it is harmful (tradition practices, e.g. rites of passage - male and female circumcision, festivals, beliefs, norms, healing/herbal medicines, etc.). Also, research reveals that children from abusive households are statistically prone to repeat or replicate similar patterns in their own parenting [1].

Child abuse as reported by Ugoji (2) do not affect only a single person or family but spill over to the entire society which could be detrimental to the growth of the society because children who have survived abuse are more likely to pass on the trauma they have experienced to their own children, and this can go on from generation to generation, if adequate precautions are not taken, which is the major focus of this study. Thus, children raised in dysfunction

family environments exhibit high prevalence of mental health issues, such as, anxiety, depression, Post-traumatic Stress disorders(PTSD), Conduct and oppositional defiant disorders [3], low self esteem, poor social adjustment, and academic difficulties [4]. Some of these behaviours are hiding under cultural pretence, values, beliefs and parenting practices that are passed down from one generation to the other. Intergenerational influences are not confined to individual families or cultures. They spread across different regions, caused by war, poverty, colonization, migration, social inequality, and family dynamics[5]. Therefore, it is a global issue experienced by all communities of the world, and Nigeria's case is not an exemption.

In the Nigerian context, the mental health of children is influenced by a complex interplay of intergenerational patterns shaped by family dynamics, socio-cultural practices, economic issue, and historical experiences which manifest in form of parenting styles, trauma transmission, communication pattern, and beliefs about mental illness. These aforementioned factors contribute to children's mental health issue, especially intergenerational transmission of behaviours, values, and psychological vulnerabilities, which affects children's holistic development and response to adversity[6]. Many

families continue to operate within inherited frameworks that may perpetuate emotional neglect, authoritarian discipline, or stigmatization of mental health issues [7]. Despite these challenges, the impact of parental education in breaking harmful cycles and promoting positive developmental outcomes can not be overemphasized. Educating parents on emotional intelligence by incorporating emotional resilience, communication skills, stress management, in children upbringing can foster healthier family dynamics and reduce the risk of intergenerational pattern and children's psychosocial issues.

This paper explores the role of parental education in breaking the circles of intergenerational transmission of negative behaviour and emotional patterns. It also discusses the implications for counseling practice and mental health intervention in Nigeria, aiming to provide a culturally relevant framework for practitioners, teachers, and policymakers.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant as it examines the crucial role of parenting education in breaking intergenerational cycles of maladaptive behaviors and promoting the mental well-being of children. In many contexts, particularly in Nigeria and similar societies, patterns of poor parenting practices often passed down from one generation to the next which contribute to psychosocial challenges in children, such as anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and behavioural disorders. By investigating how structured parenting education can interrupt these harmful patterns, this study offers a pathway for early prevention and long-term mental health resilience.

The findings will be particularly valuable to parents, caregivers, teachers, counselors, and mental health professionals seeking effective strategies to support children's psychological development. Additionally, the study can inform policymakers and curriculum developers by emphasizing the need for integrating parenting education into community-based programs and school outreach initiatives.

Overall, this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on preventive mental health strategies and underscores the importance of empowering parents with skills and understanding multidimensional approach to combat intergenerational pattern and children mental health issues in order to nurture emotionally healthy balanced children. The implications extend beyond the family unit, potentially leading to more stable, productive, and mentally resilient communities.

Limitations of the Study

As a position paper, this work is based primarily on theoretical analysis, existing literature, and reasoned argument rather than empirical investigation. Consequently, one of its primary limitations lies in

the absence of original data collection or field-based evidence. While the paper draws from established studies and real-world observations, it does not test its assumptions or proposals through direct experimentation or statistical validation.

Additionally, the perspectives presented may be influenced by the availability and scope of existing literature, which may not fully capture the diversity of parenting practices and mental health challenges across different Nigerian communities or cultural contexts. As such, the paper may not account for all socio-economic, religious, or educational variations that affect parenting styles and children's mental well-being.

Despite these limitations, the paper serves as a critical contribution to ongoing discussions on preventive mental health strategies and offers a compelling foundation for future research, policy development, and practice in the field of parenting education.

Gap in the Literature/Discourse

Despite growing concern over children's mental health issues and intergenerational patterns of dysfunctional parenting, there remains a significant gap in how parenting education is positioned as a strategic intervention, particularly in the Nigerian context. Much of the existing literature and policy focus tends to emphasize reactive approaches, such as clinical treatment or school-based behavioral correction, rather than proactive, preventive strategies rooted in the family system.

Furthermore, while research acknowledges the impact of parenting styles on children's development, there is limited integration of structured parenting education into national mental health strategies, public awareness programmes, or school-based counseling initiatives. This gap results in a missed opportunity to empower parents with the knowledge and skills necessary to break harmful cycles and foster emotionally resilient children.

This paper addresses this gap by emphasizing the urgent need to recognize parenting education not merely as a private family matter but as a public health and social development priority. It argues for the institutionalization of parenting programs as a central tool for early mental health intervention and social transformation, especially in societies experiencing intergenerational trauma, economic stress, and weak support systems.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two foundational psychological theories: Baumrind's Parenting Style Theory and Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. Together, they provide a comprehensive lens

through which to examine the role of parental education in the prevention of intergenerational psychosocial patterns and the promotion of mental health in children.

1. Baumrind's Parenting Style Theory

Diana Baumrind (8) identified four primary parenting styles which includes authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful, based on levels of responsiveness and demandingness. Her theory posits that parenting behavior significantly shapes children's emotional regulation, self-esteem, social functioning, and resilience. Authoritative parenting, which combines warmth with structure, is consistently associated with optimal child outcomes, while authoritarian and neglectful styles are linked to anxiety, aggression, and poor social skills.

In the Nigerian context, where authoritarian styles often dominate due to cultural norms and lack of formal parental education, Baumrind's framework highlights the need for informed and balanced parenting. It underscores the importance of parental awareness and training in promoting healthy psychosocial development and breaking intergenerational cycles of dysfunction.

2. Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory

Urie Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory [9] views child development as the result of interactions between the child and multiple layers of environmental influence, ranging from immediate settings (microsystem) to broader societal forces (macrosystem). Parental behavior, literacy, and education are key components of the microsystem, directly shaping a child's psychological and emotional world. The exosystem (e.g., parent's workplace, social services) and macrosystem (e.g., cultural values, socioeconomic status, and mental health stigma) also impact the child indirectly through their effects on parental behavior and available resources.

This theory is particularly relevant in the Nigerian setting, where community norms, poverty, religion, and traditional parenting ideologies deeply influence how children are raised. It emphasizes the necessity of systemic interventions including parent education, school-based counseling, and public health initiatives to create environments that support healthy development. The integration of these two theories allows for a multidimensional understanding of how parental education mediates the effects of cultural and socioeconomic factors on child development. It also provides a solid framework for designing interventions that are not only psychologically sound but also contextually and culturally relevant to the Nigerian families.

Roles of Parenting Styles and Education: Insights from Baumrind's Parenting Theory

Parenting styles play a central role in shaping a child's emotional, social, and cognitive development. Diana Baumrind's seminal theory identifies four primary parenting styles authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful each with distinct impacts on children's psychosocial outcomes.

Authoritative parenting is characterized by high responsiveness and high demands. Parents provide warmth and support while setting clear expectations. This style is consistently associated with positive child outcomes such as self-confidence, social competence, and emotional regulation. Authoritarian parenting involves high demands but low responsiveness. It often includes strict discipline, limited warmth, and expectations of unquestioning obedience. Children raised this way may exhibit anxiety, low self-esteem, or aggression. Permissive parenting is marked by high responsiveness but low demands, where parents are indulgent and set few boundaries. This can lead to impulsivity and poor self-discipline in children. Neglectful or uninvolved parenting includes low responsiveness and low demands, often resulting in children feeling unloved or unsupported, which may contribute to behavioral problems and emotional instability [8].

In the Nigerian context, authoritarian parenting is commonly practiced, largely due to cultural norms that emphasize respect for authority, obedience, and parental control [10]. While this may foster discipline, it often does so at the expense of open communication and emotional closeness. This contributes to the intergenerational transmission of fear-based obedience and emotional suppression, which can affect children's mental health and social development. Parental education significantly influences the adoption of good parenting styles. Educated parents are more likely to access information on child development, adopt nurturing strategies, and engage in positive reinforcement techniques [11]. They also tend to be more open to counseling interventions and less likely to rely on outdated or harmful practices.

In contrast, limited education or exposure to mental health literacy programme often results in rigid, authoritarian practices being perceived as the only effective approach to childrearing. This highlights the critical need for targeted parenting education programmes in Nigeria which can promote authoritative parenting while respecting cultural values.

Intergenerational Transmission of Psychosocial Patterns

In the context of psychosocial development, intergenerational transmission can include both

positive traits such as resilience, empathy, and effective communication, and negative traits, such as emotional neglect, aggression, or maladaptive coping strategies [12]. Mechanisms of intergenerational transmission are multifaceted and can be broadly categorized into behavioral, psychological, social, and biological pathways.

Behaviourally, children often model the behaviors of their caregivers through observational learning. For example, children raised in violent or emotionally unstable households may internalize these behaviors as normative [13]. Psychologically, unresolved trauma or poor emotional regulation in parents can manifest in parenting styles that promote fear, insecurity, or detachment in children [14]. Socially, cultural norms and parenting traditions reinforce certain attitudes, such as the use of harsh discipline or suppression of emotional expression, particularly within some Nigerian communities [15]. Biologically, emerging research in epigenetics suggests that traumatic experiences may result in gene expression changes that can be inherited by subsequent generations, influencing stress responses and emotional vulnerability [12].

In Nigeria, intergenerational transmission may be reinforced by a lack of mental health awareness, poverty, limited access to parental education, and strong adherence to traditional child-rearing practices. These factors can perpetuate cycles of dysfunction where emotional and psychological needs are neglected or misunderstood. Understanding these transmission mechanisms is essential for designing interventions that address root causes rather than symptoms. Counseling, psycho-education, and family-based programs can help disrupt these patterns by equipping parents with healthier strategies for emotional and behavioral regulation.

Cross-Cultural and Nigerian Examples of Intergenerational Transmission

Intergenerational transmission of psycho-social patterns is a globally observed phenomenon, which varies significantly across cultural contexts. In Western societies, research has extensively documented how childhood experiences, including parental abuse, neglect, or mental illness, contribute to the replication of dysfunctional behaviors in adulthood. For instance, studies among Holocaust survivors and their children show how trauma-related symptoms, such as hypervigilance and emotional suppression, can be passed down through both behavioural modeling and biological imprinting [12]. In collectivist cultures such as Japan and China, intergenerational transmission often takes the form of rigid family hierarchies and emotional restraint. Children are socialized to prioritize familial duty over individual expression, sometimes at the cost of emotional well-being [16]. Similarly, in Latin

American cultures, traditional gender roles and authoritarian parenting are commonly transferred intergenerationally, often reinforced by religious and societal norms [17].

In the Nigerian, intergenerational transmission occurs within a complex interplay of traditional values, religion, and socioeconomic challenges. Harsh discipline, emotional suppression, and authoritarian parenting are frequently passed from one generation to the next as culturally sanctioned practices [15, 18]. Many parents, having experienced strict or punitive upbringing themselves, view such methods as necessary for instilling discipline and respect, despite their adverse effects on children's mental health. Moreover, stigma surrounding mental health issues in Nigeria contributes to a culture of silence, where emotional problems are dismissed or spiritualized rather than addressed through psychological support. This often leads to under-diagnosed psychosocial issues in children and adolescents, which in turn influence their future parenting behavior and emotional resilience [4].

These examples highlight the universality of intergenerational transmission while emphasizing the need for culturally specific interventions. In Nigeria, addressing these patterns requires not only parental education but also broader efforts to eradicate harmful cultural norms through counselling and improve access to mental health services.

Types of Children Psychosocial Issues

Some of the common types of psycho-social issues in children, which can affect their emotional, social, and behavioural development include:

1. Anxiety Disorders e.g. Generalized anxiety, separation anxiety, social anxiety, and specific phobias.
2. Depressive Disorders e.g. Persistent sadness or irritability, low self-esteem and loss of interest in activities.
3. Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) e.g. Difficulty focusing, impulsivity, and hyperactivity.
4. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) e.g. Challenges with communication, difficulty with social interactions, and repetitive behaviours.
5. Behavioral Disorders e.g. Oppositional Defiant Disorder (ODD), Conduct Disorder (CD), and Aggression or rule-breaking behaviours.
6. Family Dysfunction/Familial issues or problems (Parental conflicts, separation, or divorce).
7. Trauma- and Stressor- Related Disorders (e.g. PTSD - Resulting from traumatic experience, accidents, or violence and flashbacks, nightmares, emotional numbness, hyperarousal)

8. Substance Use Issues (in older children/adolescents) e.g. Early experimentation with drugs or alcohol, and often linked to peer pressure or coping with stress.

9. Low Self-Esteem and Identity Issues e.g. Common during adolescence, and can affect confidence and social functioning.

10. Suicidal Behaviour.

Causes of Psycho-social Issues in Children

Psychosocial issues in children are often the result of a complex interplay of biological, psychological, and environmental factors. These issues can significantly affect a child's emotional development, behavior, social interactions, and mental well-being.

One of the primary causes stems from the family environment. Parental conflict, separation, or divorce can create a sense of instability and insecurity, leading to anxiety, depression, or behavioral issues in children [19, 20]. Additionally, parenting styles play a crucial role; authoritarian or overprotective approaches may suppress a child's autonomy, while inconsistent discipline or lack of emotional support may contribute to confusion, low self-esteem and low academic achievement [21]. Furthermore, when parents themselves struggle with mental health issues or substance abuse, it can further disrupt the emotional environment of the home and negatively impact the child [22].

Socioeconomic factors also contribute significantly. Children living in poverty often experience chronic stress due to financial insecurity, poor nutrition, overcrowded living conditions, and limited access to quality education and healthcare. These stressors can impair cognitive development and increase vulnerability to emotional disturbances [23]. Exposure to violence, crime, or social unrest in the community can foster fear, trauma, and aggressive behaviors [24].

The educational environment can either be a source of support or a cause of distress. In schools where bullying, discrimination, or peer rejection is prevalent, children may feel isolated or victimized. Academic difficulties, learning disabilities, and high expectations without adequate support can lead to frustration, low motivation, and feelings of inadequacy. Negative relationships with teachers or school staff may further exacerbate these challenges [25].

Biological and developmental factors must also be considered. Some children may have a genetic predisposition to mental health conditions such as anxiety, depression, or attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Neurodevelopmental disorders, chronic illnesses, and physical disabilities can affect a child's self-image, peer relationships, and coping

abilities, making them more susceptible to psychosocial issues [26]. Lastly, cultural and societal pressures play a role, particularly in settings where children are expected to conform to rigid gender roles or social norms. Stigma associated with mental health issues may also prevent families from seeking help, allowing problems to escalate [27].

In summary, the causes of psycho-social issues in children are multifaceted, encompassing familial, socioeconomic, educational, biological, and cultural dimensions. Addressing these root causes requires a comprehensive and collaborative approach involving families, teachers, healthcare providers, and community support systems. In this paper, some of these children's psycho-social issues shall be explored and their implications/consequences on the children's mental health.

Post-traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)

One of the most severe psychological disorders that the children may experience is the Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). It is a severe mental health condition that develops after a child is exposed to traumatic experiences involving actual or perceived threats to life, safety, or emotional well-being. Several factors can directly or indirectly contribute to post-traumatic stress disorder in children and this include physical or sexual abuse, emotional neglect, witnessing domestic violence, natural disasters, serious accidents, or the sudden loss of a loved one, and poor parenting styles.

PTSD in children is marked by four main categories of symptoms: intrusive re-experiencing of the trauma (such as flashbacks or nightmares), avoidance of trauma-related reminders, negative alterations in mood and cognition, and heightened arousal (such as irritability, hyper-vigilance, or sleep difficulties) [8]. These symptoms can interfere significantly with a child's emotional regulation, social relationships, and academic performance. Children who have experienced abuse and neglect often develop a distorted view of themselves and the world. Physical abuse may lead to chronic fear or aggression, while emotional neglect can result in low self-worth and difficulties forming secure attachments. Prolonged exposure to such stressors during critical developmental stages can have lasting effects on the brain, especially areas related to memory, emotion regulation, and stress response [9, 23].

PTSD symptoms in these children often overlap with other disorders, such as anxiety, depression, or attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), making diagnosis and treatment more complex. Early identification and trauma-informed intervention are essential to support recovery. Evidence-based therapies such as Trauma-Focused Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (TF-CBT), play therapy, and

family-based interventions have proven effective in helping children process trauma and build resilience [11].

If not addressed early, these symptoms can evolve into chronic psychological and social issues, including anxiety disorders, depression, substance abuse, and impaired interpersonal relationships in adolescence and adulthood. These symptoms also impair the child's ability to function in daily life and contribute to behavioral issues such as aggression, withdrawal, or hypervigilance. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (5th ed.; DSM-5), these symptoms can persist for months or years if left untreated and often overlap with other mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety [28].

The most concern is the potential for intergenerational transmission of trauma. Children who do not receive adequate support and intervention may carry unresolved trauma into adulthood, affecting their parenting and perpetuating cycles of dysfunction and mental health disorders [12]. Early intervention through trauma-informed counseling and supportive family environments is therefore critical.

Alcohol, Substance Abuse and Psychosocial Issues in Adolescents

Alcohol and substance abuse by children and adolescents are of great concern in the recent times globally. The use of these harmful substances can significantly impact their mental health. These influences manifest through biological, psycho-social factors and the consequences on these younger ones often lead to long-term developmental, emotional, and behavioural challenges. Simply put, alcohol and substance abuse by these young ones may lead to many environmental and societal problems in form of criminal behaviour, accidents, injuries, behavioural disorders and health depreciation. Research reveals that peer pressure and low self-esteem can contribute significantly to alcohol and substance usage among the adolescents [29]. The use of illicit substances such as opioids, marijuana, caffeine and alcohol, among others impairs daily activities or cause notable distress according to Diagnostic Statistical Manual (DSM-5) of mental disorders [30]. Also, using substances like Cannabis and alcohol during adolescence was found to affect brain development, memory, concentration, and decision-making [31]. In addition, substance use is strongly correlated with anxiety, depression, psychosis, and suicidal ideation among the youth [32].

Furthermore, it was discovered that multiple substance use exacerbates psychosocial problems which could be as a result of dysfunction family structure, poor socioeconomic status background and poor parenting involvement. The recent research

conducted among Senior Secondary School students in Lagos, Nigeria reported that 52.7% and 36.4% adolescents sampled consumed tramadol and marijuana respectively [33]. Another study observed that 6.9% to 17.3% of secondary school students in Ilorin, Nigeria mostly use tramadol, marijuana, and alcohol. It was also gathered that 22.1% substance-using adolescents show higher psychological distress, psychiatric morbidity, and functional impairment [34]. According to them, the risk and protective factors include gender (men of old age), peer influence, family structure, parental substance use (Intergenerational pattern) and poor parental monitoring.

Consequently, among the undergraduate in Nigeria, it is not uncommon to see females and the male counterparts engaging in substance usage, such as codeine, cocaine, heroine, *speed*, *AZT*, *ecstasy*, rofenol, fentanyl, *meth*, *oxy* or worst case inhaling glue to get them high. Some of them even mix alcohol and marijuana together. It was reported in the news by a popular broadcasting station that some youths were found in the streets of Lagos using substances such as *colos*, mixing alcohol with marijuana and other harmful chemical substances claiming to be enjoying themselves.

The reasons for all these maladaptive behaviours displayed by the youths are not far-fetched. Many of them come from uninvolved parental background or dysfunctional family. Many parents, especially with high socio-economic status are too busy for proper monitoring of their children, so they are absent in their children's lives. Unfortunately, some other people such as peers, irresponsible men, social media, etc, are there to shape the child's world view. At age 12, a child's curiosities, fantasies and identities are already formed. Thus, attempting core parenting in teenage years may meet with a "brick wall" which might end up with a fractious relationship with them.

Suicidal Behaviour, Depression and Intergenerational Patterns

The influence of intergenerational patterns on children and adolescents' suicidal behaviours and depression are imminent, especially within families where mental health disorders, trauma, or maladaptive coping mechanisms (e.g. substance abuse) are prevalent. The World Health Organisation has affirmed that suicide is a leading cause of death among adolescents worldwide [35]. A research also confirmed that 50% of adolescents with depression battle with some level of suicidal ideation [36]. Sigmund Freud said that suicide is a form of aggression turned inward, an introjected, ambivalently cathected love object. This means that, no other person, other than the victims, decide and perpetuate the deadly act on them. Thus, suicidal acts happen impulsively during the moments of crisis in

order to deal with the life stresses/stressors. WHO reported that there is a correlation between suicide and mental disorders (e.g. depression and alcohol use disorders), especially in the high income countries. It was gathered that multiple psychosocial factors such as sexual abuse, physical attack and involvement in physical fights significantly predicts suicidal behaviour [37]. Other risk factors include, but not limited to the underlisted are; aggression, constant bullying, child abuse, chemical imbalance in a person's brain, chemical dependency, combination of depression with use of drugs/dependency, combination of depression with use of drugs/alcohol (e.g lethal), Domestic violence, substance use, poor family patterns, loss of valued relationship, low self-esteem, terminal illness, chronic illness (e.g. schizophrenia, depression, etc), and unachievement of social expectation [38].

One of the major risk factors of suicide is Depression, otherwise known as major depressive disorder or clinical depression [28]. It is the second class of mood disorders along with Manic episodes. Various genetic, biological, environmental, and other factors have been associated with these mood disorders, including chemical imbalances in the brain (in the case of bipolar disorder). The risk factors include environmental factors and may also be hereditary (intergenerational pattern). It is characterised by emotional problems which impairs the daily activities of the victims.

In summary, the implications of PTSD and other psychosocial issues in children are far-reaching, affecting every aspect of their development and well-being. Addressing these challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach involving mental health professionals, teachers, and caregivers/guardians to provide a stable, supportive, and therapeutic environment.

Interventions for Intergenerational Patterns and Children's Psycho-social Issues

Intervening in intergenerational patterns and psycho-social issues in children requires a multifaceted and systemic approach that targets both the family unit and individual psychosocial development. These patterns, often transmitted through parenting styles, unresolved trauma, and socio-cultural norms, can perpetuate emotional, behavioral, and relational dysfunctions across generations [12]. Effective intervention begins with parental education, which plays a critical role in reshaping maladaptive behaviors and enhancing parent-child relationships. Parental education programs often focus on equipping caregivers with positive parenting skills, emotional regulation techniques, and non-violent discipline strategies. Such interventions help parents become more responsive to their children's emotional needs and reduce the risk of perpetuating harmful

parenting behaviors [39]. Programs such as the Positive Parenting Program (Triple P) have demonstrated efficacy in reducing child behavioural problems and improving parental competence and confidence [40].

In addition to parental training, family therapy serves as a core intervention strategy. Intergenerational family therapy, for instance, explores patterns of behavior passed down through generations and works to restructure dysfunctional family dynamics [41]. Through therapeutic dialogue and systemic restructuring, families are supported in breaking negative cycles and establishing healthier relational patterns. Narrative therapy also contributes by helping individuals and families reconstruct their life stories in empowering ways, detaching from inherited negative identities [42].

For children directly affected by psycho-social issues such as anxiety, depression, and trauma, child-focused therapies are essential. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) has been widely validated for addressing emotional regulation and cognitive distortions in children [43]. Play therapy is particularly useful for younger children who may struggle to articulate their emotions verbally, providing a safe environment for expression and processing [44]. Additionally, trauma-informed interventions that recognize the impact of early adverse experiences can foster resilience and psychological healing [45]. Importantly, interventions must be culturally sensitive and contextually relevant, particularly in settings like Nigeria, where social norms, economic pressures, and access to mental health services vary significantly. Community-based programs and school counselling initiatives can help bridge service gaps, promoting early identification and support for at-risk children and families.

Overall, breaking intergenerational patterns and addressing psycho-social issues in children requires a coordinated approach that combines education, therapy, and systemic change. When effectively implemented, these interventions can foster healthier families and promote the psychological well-being of future generations.

Parenting Education in the Prevention of Children's Psychosocial Issues

Parenting education is increasingly recognized as a vital strategy in preventing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and addressing a range of psychosocial issues in children. By equipping caregivers with the knowledge and skills to foster secure attachments and create a nurturing home environment, parenting education programs help mitigate the adverse effects of trauma exposure. Research demonstrates that when parents are educated on trauma-informed care and effective

communication, children are less likely to develop chronic stress responses and behavioral issues associated with traumatic experiences [46]. At the heart of parenting education is the emphasis on early detection and intervention. Teachers and educators teach parents to identify early signs of distress or unusual behavior in their children that may indicate emerging trauma-related issues. For instance, an informed parent is more likely to notice changes in sleep patterns, mood disturbances, or social withdrawal, and can then take timely action to seek professional help or adjust their caregiving practices [47]. This proactive stance not only addresses immediate symptoms but also works to build a resilient foundation that can buffer the child from more severe psychosocial difficulties later in life.

Moreover, parenting education programmes emphasize the importance of emotional attunement and the development of secure attachments. By learning strategies to provide consistent emotional support and effective stress management, parents can help their children develop adaptive coping mechanisms, which are crucial for navigating both daily stressors and more significant traumatic events. In addition, parenting education often includes training in effective communication and problem-solving skills. Parents learn how to engage in open dialogues with their children, validating their emotional experiences and reinforcing their capacity to overcome adversity. This communicative approach helps alleviate feelings of isolation and confusion that often accompany trauma, fostering a sense of stability and belonging that is essential for healthy psychosocial development [46].

Ultimately, parenting education serves as a preventive measure by preparing parents, guardians or caregivers to create environments that foster resilience, emotional regulation, and healthy social interactions. These educational initiatives not only reduce the immediate risk of PTSD and other psychosocial issues in children, but also contribute to the long-term psycho-social well-being of children, making them a critical component of community health programs and early childhood interventions.

IMPLICATIONS FOR COUNSELLING

The integration of parenting education into counselling practice holds significant implications for the prevention and management of psycho-social issues in children. Counsellors play a critical role not only in providing therapeutic support to children but also in guiding parents to become effective agents of emotional healing and resilience within the family system. First, counsellors can incorporate parenting education as a preventive tool by organizing workshops and psycho-educational sessions that focus on trauma-informed parenting. These sessions can empower parents with the knowledge to

understand how trauma affects child development and behavior, enabling them to respond with empathy and appropriate interventions rather than punitive reactions. This preventive approach is particularly relevant in post-conflict or high-stress environments, where many children are at increased risk of trauma exposure [48].

Second, in counselling settings, professionals can adopt a family systems approach that includes parents in the therapeutic process. This not only reinforces the child's support network but also helps parents reflect on their own stress responses, attachment patterns, and emotional regulation strategies. By working with both children and parents, counsellors can help break intergenerational cycles of trauma and maladaptive coping [49], through family therapy interventions.

Third, counselling interventions can emphasize strengthening the parent-child relationship as a key element of healing. Attachment-based therapies, for instance, support parents in building secure emotional bonds with their children which can essential buffer against PTSD and psycho-social dysfunction. When parents learn to co-regulate emotions with their children, they help create a safe space where children feel heard, protected, and understood [50].

Furthermore, counsellors can advocate for systemic support by collaborating with schools, religious institutions, and community organizations to integrate parenting education into broader mental health initiatives. This multidisciplinary approach not only broadens access but also normalizes mental health care, reducing stigma and encouraging early engagement with support services. In summary, the counselling profession has a vital role in leveraging parenting education as both a preventive and therapeutic tool. By equipping parents with trauma-informed skills and fostering strong family connections, counsellors contribute meaningfully to the mental health and psychosocial well-being of children, especially those navigating the effects of trauma.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To effectively address post-traumatic stress disorder and other psycho-social issues in children while also breaking the intergenerational cycle of trauma, several key recommendations should be implemented across mental health, educational, and community systems:

1. There is a need to integrate parenting education into community mental health programmes. Government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and mental health institutions should prioritize the development of structured, trauma-informed parenting workshops that are culturally appropriate and accessible to families in both urban

and rural settings. These programmes should focus on building parents' capacity to provide emotionally supportive, stable environments and to recognize the early signs of psychological distress in children.

2. Counselling services must adopt a family-centered, trauma-informed approach. Mental health professionals should be trained to involve parents actively in the therapeutic process, not only as supporters of their children's recovery but also as individuals who may need healing themselves. By addressing parental trauma and emotional regulation, counselling can help prevent the unconscious transmission of dysfunctional coping mechanisms to the next generation.

3. Schools should play an active role in promoting parenting education. Through partnerships with mental health professionals, educational institutions can offer regular seminars and workshops that educate parents about child development, positive discipline, and emotional communication. This strategy provides an early intervention point, reaching families before more severe mental health issues emerge.

4. Interdisciplinary collaboration is also essential. Mental health practitioners, teachers and educators, counsellors, clinical psychologists, psychiatrists, social workers, religious leaders, and community-based organizations should work together to form a cohesive support network for families. This collaborative model ensures consistency in messaging, enhances the reach of parenting education initiatives, and creates multiple avenues through which parents can access guidance and support.

Finally, policies should be enacted to support ongoing research and funding for parenting education programs, particularly in regions affected by conflict, poverty, or systemic trauma. By institutionalizing these recommendations, societies can move toward breaking cycles of trauma and fostering healthier, more resilient generations.

CONCLUSION

Parenting education serves as a powerful and preventative tool in addressing post-traumatic stress disorder and psycho-social issues in children. By equipping parents with the skills to recognize early signs of trauma, respond with empathy, and foster secure, supportive environments, such education enhances the emotional resilience and mental well-being of children. The role of parents as frontline caregivers makes their involvement in trauma prevention and intervention indispensable. Importantly, parenting education also plays a critical role in disrupting the intergenerational transmission of trauma and maladaptive psychosocial patterns. When parents have unresolved trauma or lack emotional regulation skills, these can inadvertently be

passed down to their children through neglect, harsh discipline, or emotional unavailability. Through structured education and counselling interventions, parents can become aware of these patterns, learn healthier ways of relating to their children, and begin the process of healing both themselves and future generations.

Counselling professionals, therefore, have a vital responsibility in integrating parenting education into therapeutic practice. Trauma-informed, family-centered counselling approaches empower parents to become active participants in their children's emotional recovery, while also addressing their own psychological needs. Ultimately, embedding parenting education into mental health frameworks offers a sustainable pathway to breaking intergenerational cycles of trauma and fostering long-term psychosocial well-being in families and communities.

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